

RESEARCH PAPER

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Quality and Shelf Life of Aonla (*Emblica officinalis* Gaertn.) Juice Stored at Divergent Temperature Regimes

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Received:

2025/06/08

Accepted:

2025/06/24

Published:

2025/06/27

Abstract

Aonla is renowned for its exceptional nutritional and therapeutic properties, rich in ascorbic acid and polyphenols. Its vitamin C content often exceeds 500 mg100g⁻¹ making it ten times higher than that of oranges. It is highly perishable and cannot be stored beyond a week at ambient temperature. In this study, juice was extracted from fresh and stored aonla fruits using a rack and cloth press, followed by heat processing at 90°C for 1 minute and subsequently pasteurized at 75-80°C for 20 minutes. The processed juice bottles were stored at ambient temperature (18-28°C, 70 % RH), zero energy cool chamber (15-18°C, 90 % RH) and cold store (5-7°C and 80-85% RH). The juice recovery was 67 % from fresh fruits and 62 % from stored fruits. Shelf-life studies revealed that juice held at ambient temperature remained marketable up to four months, whereas the juice stored in a cool chamber and cold store had shelf life beyond six months with better quality retention. The TSS and ascorbic acid declined gradually, whereas acidity, tannins, reducing, total sugars and non-enzymatic browning in aonla juice increased during storage.

Keywords: Ambient storage; Aonla juice; Cold store; Cool chamber; Quality

Introduction

Aonla or Indian gooseberry (*Emblica officinalis* Gaertn.) is indigenous to India and is widely acclaimed for its nutritional and therapeutic properties. The vitamin C content of aonla often exceeds 500 mg100g⁻¹ and is almost ten times than that of oranges, that are widely recognized as good source of vitamin C. Aonla has been used in many Ayurvedic preparations such as *Triphala*, *Chyavanprash* and *Rasayana* owing to the high contents of vitamin C and phenolic compounds, believed to impart the therapeutic properties upon consuming the traditional medicines containing this fruit. The leucoanthocyanins, along with the high level of phenolics, are believed to impart stability to vitamin C content in aonla. The physiological benefits of consuming aonla fruits and their products are attributed to the phenolic compounds, particularly flavonoids. Among the phenolic compounds in aonla, tannins are of significant importance, and the major tannins identified by HPLC analysis include gallic acid, pyrogallol, corilagin, ellagic acid and chebulagic acid and also quercetin, a well-studied flavonoid known for its immense health-protective properties (Zhao et al., 2015).

Indian gooseberry fruit incorporated with spices such as black pepper, turmeric and ginger extracts reported a significant increase in thymus weight, showing increased T cell differentiation in Cyclophosphamide-treated mice. The findings also revealed that a marginal increase in WBC count and bone marrow cellularity was directly proportional to the concentration of the drink, indicating recovery of immunity (Gomez et al., 2024). Aonla fruits are highly perishable in nature as they cannot be stored under ambient conditions beyond a week. Enormous physico-chemical changes take place during the post-harvest handling, storage, transportation and marketing of the fruits,

which result in heavy losses. Infection of aonla fruits by the fungus *Aspergillus flavus* is one of the major reasons for spoilage.

In North India, the harvesting period of aonla extends from October to February. Incidence of *Aspergillus flavus* is observed in aonla fruits throughout the marketing period which indicates that the fungus can survive in a wide range of temperatures. The fungus enters the fruit through injuries, wounds and bruises on the fruit which indicates the necessity of careful post-harvest handling of aonla fruits. The skin/peel of aonla fruit is so soft and delicate that even a slight injury or bruise can lead to fungal growth and subsequent decay. The symptoms appear as raised yellow spots initially, and as time progresses, the whole fruit is covered with ash coloured powdery coating of the fungus. In order to avoid market losses, immediate disposal of the fruits is inevitable. During seasons of bumper yields and subsequent market gluts, huge post-harvest losses are a recurring phenomenon in the major markets in India. It is reported that *Aspergillus* spp. can infect weakened fruits that have been wounded. It also infects fruits during harvesting, washing, handling, grading, storage and marketing, up until the fruit is bought by a consumer (Zakaria, 2024). When fruits are wounded, the cells release nutrients and water, leading to congenial conditions for fungal growth. Postharvest rots in fruits can result in huge losses during storage and the supply chain, as spoiled fruits become unmarketable. Therefore, processing of aonla fruits into a variety of products can reduce the post-harvest losses.

Among the various products, aonla juice holds potential due to its high nutritional value and better shelf life when properly processed and stored, offering an efficient way to utilise surplus produce and ensure year-round availability, thus helping to prevent price debacle and market glut. Aonla is not a choice fruit of the vast majority of the population owing to the high acidity and astringency of the fruit. However, it offers immense potential for blending with less nutritious fruit juices. Thermal processing is one of the widely adopted techniques of food preservation, even though it has adverse effects on phytochemicals and the sensory quality. It is an economically viable method of food preservation, especially in developing and underdeveloped nations. Heat pasteurization can extend the shelf life of fruit juices by inactivation of microbes and undesirable enzymes (Azofeifa et al., 2015).

Bhattacharjee et al. (2011) reported that pasteurization at 80 °C was optimum for preservation of aonla juice under ambient conditions. Good quality juice can be prepared from aonla fruits preserved by steeping for up to 10 days in water, which could retain acceptable quality for up to 4 months at ambient storage (Bhattacharjee et al., 2013). The range of temperature for thermal pasteurization of aonla juice is 75-95 °C, 100 °C, 90 °C, and the level of preservatives is 500 ppm of SO₂ (Tewari et al., 2023). As consumers tend to be more health conscious in recent times, there is increased demand for natural fruit juices without synthetic food additives. Hence, an attempt was made to evaluate the quality and shelf life of pasteurized aonla juice obtained from fresh and stored fruits (16 days) without adding any synthetic preservatives and subsequently holding at different temperature regimes.

Materials and methods

Aonla fruits of cv. Chakaiya were obtained from the fruit and vegetable market, Azadpur, New Delhi. Good quality, sound fruits free of bruises, blemishes and decay, were selected and transported to the Division of Post-Harvest Technology, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi. About half of the fruits in this lot which formed the fresh fruits were used for juice preparation while the other half was pretreated with 2.5% Virosoil Agro (an eco- friendly biocide containing 12.5% hydrogen peroxide and 0.01% silver nitrate as active ingredients) for 5 minutes and held in cold store (5-7°C and 80-85% RH) for a period of 16 days formed the stored fruits from which juice was prepared. Both the fresh and stored fruits were cleaned and washed separately.

The washed fruits were crushed in a grater and juice was extracted separately by a hydraulic rack and cloth press at a pressure of 200 kg/sq. cm. The extracted juice from both fresh and stored fruits was heat processed separately at 90°C for 1 minute and was filled separately in clean sterilized glass bottles of 200 ml capacity and the filled bottles were crown-corked. The crown-corked bottles containing juice were pasteurized at 75-80°C for 20 minutes. The bottles containing juice from both fresh and stored fruits were held under three different storage conditions viz. ambient (RT) (in the month of February, at 18 -28 °C and 70 % RH), zero energy cool chamber (ZECC, 15-18 °C and 90% RH) (Roy, 1997) and cold store (CS) (5-7°C and 80-85% RH) as depicted in Fig. 3. The various steps in the preparation of aonla juice are outlined in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Flow chart for the preparation of Aonla juice

Fig. 2. Aonla fruits infected with *Aspergillus flavus*

Fig. 3. Aonla juice after six months at ambient, cool chamber and cold store

Aonla juice from both fresh and stored fruits held under the different temperature regimes was analyzed for chemical composition, viz. acidity (AOAC, 1998), total soluble solids (TSS), reducing and total sugars, tannins and ascorbic acid (Ranganna, 1997). Non-enzymatic browning was determined by measuring the optical density values at 440 nm using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu 1800 series, Kyoto, Japan). The data were statistically analyzed following a Completely Randomized Design using WASP software with a critical difference at 5 %.

Results and discussion

The juice recovery from fresh and stored aonla fruits was found to be 67 and 62 per cent, respectively. The higher juice recovery from fresh fruits may be due to the higher moisture content in fresh fruits. This was significantly higher than the juice yield reported in the cultivars NA-7 and Desi, which were 50.1 and 48.1 %, respectively (Sharma et al., 2020).

Table 1. Total soluble solids (°Brix) of aonla juice from fresh and stored fruits during storage

Treatments	Initial	2 MAS	4 MAS	6 MAS
Juice from fresh fruit +RT	8.10	8.00	7.50	7.32*
Juice from fresh fruit +CC		8.05	7.70	7.46
Juice from fresh fruit +CS		8.05	7.80	7.54
Juice from stored fruit +RT	7.50	7.35	7.14	6.82*
Juice from stored fruit +CC		7.43	7.22	6.92
Juice from stored fruit +CS		7.45	7.28	7.04
Mean		7.72	7.44	7.18
S. Em±		0.08	0.12	0.05
CD (0.05)		0.22	0.37	0.05

RT- Room Temperature; CC-Cool chamber; CS-Cold store; MAS-Month after storage; CD-Critical difference; S. Em- Standard error of the mean; *-Unmarketable

The TSS, ascorbic acid, tannins, total and reducing sugars were higher in the juice prepared from fresh fruits, whereas the acidity was higher in the juice prepared from stored fruits. The lower levels of TSS, ascorbic acid, tannins, total and reducing sugars in the juice from stored fruits might be attributed to their degradation during storage of the fruits, mainly due to the adverse effects of oxidation and also, due to the biochemical reactions that occurred during storage. The higher acidity of juice from stored fruits might be due to the loss of moisture from aonla fruits during storage.

Table 2. Ascorbic acid content (mg/100 g) of aonla juice from fresh and stored fruits during storage

Treatments	Initial	2 MAS	4 MAS	6 MAS
Juice from fresh fruit +RT	336	256	222	185*
Juice from fresh fruit +CC		262	230	194
Juice from fresh fruit +CS		271	238	207
Juice from stored fruit +RT	278	194	164	125*
Juice from stored fruit +CC		201	172	136
Juice from stored fruit +CS		209	178	146
Mean		232	201	166
S. Em±		1.88	1.80	1.65
CD (0.05)		5.79	5.54	5.08

RT- Room Temperature; CC-Cool chamber; CS-Cold store; MAS- Month after storage; CD-Critical difference; S. Em- Standard error of the mean; *- Unmarketable

Total soluble solids (TSS) content is directly correlated with palatability (flavour) and marketability of fruits and their products. Ascorbic acid, popularly known as vitamin C, is a potent antioxidant, and its regular consumption is positively correlated with higher levels of immunity. Aonla is one of the richest sources of this vitamin among fruits. Initial TSS of aonla juice from fresh and stored fruits were 8.10 and 7.50 °Brix while the ascorbic acid contents were 336.0 and 278.0 mg100g⁻¹, respectively. The TSS and ascorbic acid in aonla juice decreased during storage (Table 1 and 2). The juice held in cold store had the maximum TSS (7.04 to 7.54 °Brix) and ascorbic acid (146 to 207 mg100g⁻¹) followed by that in cool chamber (TSS of 6.92 to 7.46 °Brix and ascorbic acid content of 136 to 194 mg100g⁻¹) and room temperature (TSS of 6.82 to 7.32 °Brix and ascorbic acid content of 125 to 185 mg100g⁻¹), after six months of storage. However, the samples held in the cold store retained higher TSS than those stored in the cool chamber and at room temperature. This may be due to the inversion of complex sugars into simpler ones which may have been accelerated at higher temperatures.

Decline in TSS might be due to interaction of chemical compounds present in the juice and also, due to increase in acidity under all storage conditions (ambient temperature, cool chamber and cold

store). Decline in ascorbic acid was higher in juice stored at room temperature compared to other storage conditions, while highest retention of ascorbic acid was observed in the samples held in cold store in the juices prepared from both stored and fresh fruits.

Table 3. Acidity (%) of aonla juice from fresh and stored fruits during storage

Treatments	Initial	2 MAS	4 MAS	6 MAS
Juice from fresh fruit +RT	2.30	2.48	2.57	2.59*
Juice from fresh fruit +CC		2.37	2.46	2.56
Juice from fresh fruit +CS		2.34	2.38	2.45
Juice from stored fruit +RT	2.65	2.80	2.87	2.90*
Juice from stored fruit +CC		2.73	2.79	2.85
Juice from stored fruit +CS		2.70	2.74	2.79
Mean		2.57	2.64	2.69
S. Em±		0.05	0.02	0.03
CD (0.05)		0.05	0.05	0.06

RT- Room Temperature; CC-Cool chamber; CS-Cold store; MAS- Month after storage; CD-Critical difference; S. Em-Standard error of the mean; *-Unmarketable

Fall in ascorbic acid might be due to degradation of ascorbic acid to dehydroascorbic acid as a result of the action of the enzyme ascorbic acid dehydrogenase which could have been accelerated by oxidative reactions. Faster rates of these reactions at higher temperatures may have led to greater decline and hence, samples held in cold store retained more ascorbic acid. Decline in TSS and ascorbic acid content of aonla juice during storage was also reported by Mehta and Rathore (1976). Fall in ascorbic acid content of pasteurized aonla juice held under ambient conditions was reported by Bhattacharjee et al. (2011). The results clearly indicate the role of storage temperature in the retention of chemical constituents of the juice. Higher retention of TSS and ascorbic acid in the juice held in cold store might be due to the beneficial effects of low temperature which hindered the biochemical reactions and the slower rate at which these reactions occurred at very low temperatures. Vitamin C is highly thermo-labile and photosensitive. Higher retention of TSS and vitamin C in passion fruit nectar stored for three months at low temperature was reported by Charan et al. (2017) which aligns with the present findings. Similar results were also obtained by Sethi et al. (1980) in kinnow mandarin juice and Rampal (1992) in lime juice.

The acidity, tannins, reducing and total sugars in aonla juice increased during storage (Table 3, 4, 5 and 6). The acidity of juice from fresh and stored fruits was 2.30 and 2.65 %, respectively. The increase in acidity might be due to the degradation of pectic substances. The juice stored at room temperature had the maximum acidity, followed by that in the cool chamber and the cold store. Higher acidity in juice stored at room temperature may be due to a faster rate of biochemical reactions at higher temperatures. After six months of storage, the content of titratable acidity of the juice stored at room temperature, cool chamber and cold store were 2.59 to 2.90, 2.56 to 2.85 and 2.45 to 2.79, respectively. Also, a decline in TSS may have contributed to an increase in titratable acidity. Similar results were obtained by Mehta and Rathore (1976) in aonla juice and Sandhu et al. (1985) in Kinnow mandarin, pineapple and orange juice concentrates.

Table 4. Tannin content (%) of aonla juice from fresh and stored fruits during storage

Treatments	Initial	2 MAS	4 MAS	6 MAS
Juice from fresh fruit +RT	2.60	2.64	2.68	2.75*
Juice from fresh fruit +CC		2.62	2.65	2.68
Juice from fresh fruit +CS		2.61	2.63	2.65
Juice from stored fruit +RT	2.52	2.57	2.61	2.68*
Juice from stored fruit +CC		2.54	2.57	2.61
Juice from stored fruit +CS		2.54	2.56	2.59
Mean		2.59	2.62	2.66
S. Em±		0.03	0.03	0.02
CD (0.05)		0.06	0.06	0.05

RT- Room Temperature; CC-Cool chamber; CS-Cold store; MAS- Month after storage; CD-Critical difference; S. Em-Standard error of the mean; *-Unmarketable

Tannins are responsible for the astringent taste of fruits and their products. Tannin content of the juice increased during storage. The initial tannin content of the juice from fresh and stored fruits was 2.67 and 2.54 %, respectively. After six months of storage, the tannin content in the product stored under ambient storage, cool chamber and cold store was 2.68 to 2.75, 2.61 to 2.68 and 2.59 to 2.65 %, respectively. Higher tannins in the juice stored under ambient conditions might be due to the conversion of polyphenols into phenolic acids due to the action of the enzyme polyphenol oxidase. The reaction may have been accelerated due to higher temperatures under ambient conditions. However, decline in polyphenols was reported in pasteurized aonla juice added with

SO₂ as preservative and subsequently stored under ambient conditions (Bhattacharjee et al., 2011). Higher tannin content in aonla juice stored at room temperature compared to that under low temperature was also observed by Jain (2001).

Table 5. Reducing sugars (%) of aonla juice from fresh and stored fruits during storage

Treatments	Initial	2 MAS	4 MAS	6 MAS
Juice from fresh fruit +RT	3.26	3.34	3.38	3.42*
Juice from fresh fruit +CC		3.30	3.35	3.40
Juice from fresh fruit +CS		3.27	3.30	3.32
Juice from stored fruit +RT	2.98	3.04	3.07	3.10*
Juice from stored fruit +CC		3.00	3.02	3.05
Juice from stored fruit +CS		2.98	3.00	3.03
Mean		3.16	3.19	3.22
S. Em±		0.03	0.08	0.03
CD (0.05)		0.06	0.22	0.06

RT- Room Temperature; CC- Cool chamber; CS-Cold store; MAS-Month after storage; CD-Critical difference; S. Em- Standard error of the mean; *-Unmarketable

Table 6. Total sugars (%) of aonla juice from fresh and stored fruits during storage

Treatments	Initial	2 MAS	4 MAS	6 MAS
Juice from fresh fruit +RT	7.18	7.30	7.36	7.40*
Juice from fresh fruit +CC		7.25	7.29	7.32
Juice from fresh fruit +CS		7.21	7.24	7.26
Juice from stored fruit +RT	6.77	6.91	6.96	6.89
Juice from stored fruit +CC		6.82	6.87	6.86
Juice from stored fruit +CS		6.79	6.83	6.83
Mean		7.05	7.09	7.09
S. Em±		0.08	0.05	0.05
CD (0.05)		0.22	0.05	0.05

RT- Room Temperature; CC-Cool chamber; CS-Cold store; MAS-Month after storage; CD-Critical difference; S. Em- Standard error of the mean; *-Unmarketable

Table 7. Non-enzymatic browning (absorbance) of aonla juice from fresh and stored fruits during storage

Treatments	Initial	2 MAS	4 MAS	6 MAS
Juice from fresh fruit +RT	0.028	0.096	0.278	0.322
Juice from fresh fruit +CC		0.059	0.106	0.173
Juice from fresh fruit +CS		0.046	0.070	0.118
Juice from stored fruit +RT	0.035	0.100	0.324	0.483
Juice from stored fruit +CC		0.066	0.124	0.192
Juice from stored fruit +CS		0.053	0.105	0.154
Mean		0.070	0.168	0.240
S. Em±		0.02	0.02	0.91
CD (0.05)		0.023	0.024	0.008

RT- Room Temperature; CC-Cool chamber; CS-Cold store; MAS-Month after storage; CD-Critical difference; S. Em- Standard error of the mean; *-Unmarketable

Natural sugars constitute more than 80 % of the total soluble solids. The major sugars found in fruits are sucrose, glucose and fructose. Aonla is not relished in the fresh form due to the low levels of natural sugars, as indicated by the TSS content of around 8 °Brix. The initial content of reducing and total sugars in aonla juice was in the range of 2.98 to 3.26 and 6.77 to 7.18 %, respectively. After six months of storage, the reducing sugar content of aonla juice stored at ambient storage, cool chamber and cold store were in the range of 3.10 to 3.42, 3.05 to 3.40 and 3.03 to 3.32 %, respectively while the total sugars were in the range of 6.89 to 7.40, 6.86 to 7.32 and 6.83 to 7.26 %, respectively under the same storage conditions. The increase in reducing and total sugars of aonla juice during storage might be attributed to the hydrolysis of polysaccharides and inversion of non-reducing sugars. Similar findings were reported by Tripathi et al. (1988) in aonla juice and Bansal and Dhawan (1993) in lemon juice.

Non-enzymatic browning (NEB) occurs as a result of the reaction of sugars and amino acids present in fruit juices. As a result of these biochemical reactions, the natural colour of fruit juices tends to darken over time. Initial values of Non-enzymatic browning (NEB) in the juice from fresh and stored fruits were 0.028 and 0.035, respectively. After six months of storage, the NEB values (absorbance) in the product stored under ambient storage, cool chamber and cold store were 0.322 to 0.483, 0.173 to 0.192 and 0.118 to 0.154, respectively. The juice from stored fruits had significantly higher NEB as compared to that from fresh fruits. This could be due to the brown spots on the fruits during storage as result of chilling injury at low temperatures. The NEB of aonla juice increased during

storage (Table 7). This could be due to the formation of furfural and hydroxy furfural by aerobic and anaerobic degradation of ascorbic acid or reaction between ascorbic acid and organic acids or due to the Maillard reaction. The juice held in the cold store exhibited significantly lower NEB as compared to that in the cool chamber and room temperature. Similar results were obtained by Sawamura et al. (1991) and Weiss (1977) in fruit juices.

Aonla juice from both fresh and stored fruits held at room temperature had a shelf life of around six months, whereas the juice stored in a cool chamber and cold store retained its quality beyond six months, which clearly indicates the effect of temperature on the quality and shelf life of the juice. The extended shelf life of the product in a cool chamber and cold store might be due to the slower rate of biochemical reactions at low temperatures. However, the shelf life of the product stored at room temperature was four months. This could be due to the increase in non-enzymatic browning in the product over time, and also due to the fact that the juice was not added with any synthetic preservatives. Aonla juice pasteurized at temperatures less than 100 °C and added with 500 ppm SO₂, when stored under ambient conditions at 18-36 °C and 40-80 % relative humidity, could be stored up to nine months (Bhattacharjee et al., 2011).

Conclusion

Aonla juice from fresh fruits had higher levels of nutrients and better quality as compared to that from stored fruits. Fresh fruits yielded higher juice content than the stored ones. Aonla juice extracted using a rack and cloth press, followed by heat processing and subsequently pasteurized, without any synthetic preservatives, had a shelf life of four months under ambient conditions while holding the product in cool chamber and cold store resulted in a shelf life more than six months. Storage of aonla juice at low temperature (cold store and cool chamber) was effective in the retention of nutrients and maintaining quality. The acidity, tannins, reducing sugars, total sugars and NEB in aonla juice increased during storage whereas the TSS and ascorbic acid decreased.

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Author Contributions

GS, KDS and PP conceived the concept, wrote and approved the manuscript.

Acknowledgements

Not applicable.

Funding

Not applicable.

Availability of data and materials

Not applicable.

Competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

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Citation: Gomez S, Khuridiya DS and Prasad P (2025) Quality and Shelf Life of Aonla (*Emblica officinalis* Gaertn.) Juice Stored at Divergent Temperature Regimes. *Environmental Science Archives* 4(1): 381-388.